

Supplementary Information

Supply and demand of nature-based materials for construction in Thimphu, Bhutan until 2050

Regional Environmental Change

Authors: Arushi Gupta^{*1}; Anne Holsten¹; Alisa Schneider¹; Felix Exton-Smith¹; Philipp Misselwitz¹

¹ Bauhaus der Erde gGmbH, Oberlandstr. 26-35, 12099 Berlin

*Arushi Gupta: gupta@bauhauserde.org

Table S1. Material layers and global warming potential for three building typologies in Thimphu City, for conventional (CV) and nature-based (NB) construction.

THIMPHU, BHUTAN		LOW-RISE				MID-RISE				HIGH-RISE			
Building components		GWP (kg CO2/total)	Material layers	layer thickness (m)	total surface or volume	GWP (kg CO2/total)	Material layers	layer thickness (m)	total surface or volume	GWP (kg CO2/total)	Material layers	layer thickness (m)	total surface or volume
Floor Slab	CV	27,498	fired tiles cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,3 0,05 0,2	81 m ²	66,759	fired tiles cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,4 0,05 0,2	154 m ²	219,099	fired tiles cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,5 0,05 0,2	413 m ²
	NB	26,766	wooden flooring cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,3 0,05 0,2	81 m ²	65,653	wooden flooring cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,4 0,05 0,2	154 m ²	215,422	wooden flooring cement screed bitumen foil reinforced concrete cement screed gravel/sand	0,02 0,03 0,001 0,5 0,05 0,2	413 m ²

Exterior Walls	CV	27,809	interior: gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks infill exterior: cement plaster	0,01 0,25 0,02	171 m ²	82,412	interior: gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks infill exterior: cement plaster	0,01 0,25 0,02	508 m ²	282,318	interior: gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks infill exterior: cement plaster	0,01 0,25 0,02	1740 m ²
	NB	5,774	interior: clay plaster earth blocks infill Exterior: lime hemp plaster	0,02 0,3 0,02	177 m ²	24,941	interior: lime hemp plaster timber studs hemcrete blocks infill exterior: lime hemp plaster	0,01 0,24 0,24 0,02	513 m ²	109,754	interior: clay building board cross laminated timber (CLT) bitumen foil wood-fiber insulation panel exterior: lime-hemp plaster	0,02 0,2 0,001 0,08 0,02	1755 m ²
Interior Walls non-bearing	CV	11,596	gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks gypsum plaster	0,01 0,125 0,01	147 m ²	34,760	gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks gypsum plaster	0,01 0,125 0,01	440 m ²	149,819	gypsum plaster fired terracotta bricks gypsum plaster	0,01 0,125 0,01	1896 m ²
	NB	1,903	clay plaster timber studs earth-blocks infill clay plaster	0,02 0,12 0,12 0,02	158 m ²	9,214	clay plaster timber studs hemcrete-blocks infill clay plaster	0,02 0,12 0,12 0,02	500 m ²	12,551	clay plaster timber studs hemcrete-blocks infill clay plaster	0,02 0,12 0,12 0,02	562 m ²
Interior Walls bearing	CV		NA				NA				NA		
	NB		NA				NA			77,578	clay plaster CLT clay plaster	0,02 0,3 0,02	1263 m ²

Core Walls	CV		NA			54,789	gypsum plaster reinforced concrete gypsum plaster	0,01 0,25 0,01	222 m ²	232,607	gypsum plaster reinforced concrete gypsum plaster ringbeam: reinforced concrete	0,01 0,25 0,01	810 m ²
	NB		-			16,721	clay plaster ringbeam: reinforced concrete earth blocks infill clay plaster	0,02 0,36 0,36 0,02	232 m ²	133,217	clay plaster CLT clay plaster ringbeam: reinforced concrete	0,02 0,3 0,02	841 m ²
Floors	CV	17,625	fired tiles cement screed reinforced concrete	0,02 0,07 0,16	89 m ²	90,279	fired tiles cement screed reinforced concrete	0,02 0,07 0,16	458 m ²	460,864	fired tiles cement screed reinforced concrete	0,02 0,07 0,24	1683 m ²
	NB	2,504	wooden flooring hemp-fiber (sound) insulation wooden board timber beams loose clay infill wooden board (OSB)	0,02 0,01 0,06 0,16 0,08 0,02	81 m ²	14,008	wooden flooring hemp-fiber (sound) insulation wooden board timber beams loose clay infill wooden board	0,02 0,01 0,06 0,16 0,08 0,02	454 m ²	75,066	wooden flooring hemp-fiber (sound) insulation CLT timber battens (non-bearing) loose clay infill clay building board	0,02 0,03 0,24 0,05 0,24 0,02	1417 m ²
Roof	CV	18,184	<u>sloped parts:</u> corrugated metal sheet timber beams <u>flat parts:</u> reinforced concrete	0,0007 0,175	151 m ²	37,922	<u>sloped parts:</u> corrugated metal sheet timber beams <u>flat parts:</u> reinforced concrete	0,0007 0,175	334 m ²	140,955	<u>sloped parts:</u> corrugated metal sheet structural steel profiles <u>flat parts:</u> reinforced	0,0007 0,175	782 m ²

											concrete		
	NB	7,269	<u>sloped parts:</u> fired tiles 0,02 bitumen foil 0,001 wooden board 0,02 timber beams 0,2 hemp-fiber 0,2 insulation infill 0,02 wooden board <u>flat parts:</u> wooden board 0,02 loose clay infill 0,16 wooden beams 0,16 wooden board 0,02	151 m ²	16,213	<u>sloped parts:</u> fired tiles 0,02 bitumen foil 0,001 wooden board 0,02 timber beams 0,2 hemp-fiber 0,2 insulation infill 0,02 wooden board <u>flat parts:</u> wooden board 0,02 loose clay infill 0,16 wooden beams 0,16 wooden board 0,02	334 m ²	52,849	<u>sloped parts:</u> corrugated metal sheet 0,0007 bitumen foil 0,001 wooden board 0,02 timber battens 0,2 hemp-fiber 0,2 insulation infill 0,02 wooden board <u>flat parts:</u> wooden board 0,02 loose clay infill 0,16 wooden beams 0,02 wooden board	782 m ²			
Exterior windows & doors	CV	3,771	wooden frame window double-glazed glass concrete style elements wooden doors	-	64 m ²	21,796	wooden frame window double-glazed glass concrete style elements wooden doors	-	218 m ²	35,746	wooden frame window double-glazed glass concrete style elements wooden doors	-	573 m ²
	NB	3,073	wooden frame window double-glazed glass wooden style elements wooden doors	-	64 m ²	16,593	wooden frame window double-glazed glass wooden style elements	-	218 m ²	25,752	wooden frame window double-glazed glass wooden style elements wooden doors	-	573 m ²

							wooden doors						
Columns & beams	CV	9,692	reinforced concrete beams reinforced concrete columns	-	10 m3	62,153	reinforced concrete beams reinforced concrete columns	-	22 m3	127,032	reinforced concrete beams reinforced concrete columns	-	132 m3
	NB	1,914	timber beams timber columns	-	8 m3	19,585	timber beams timber columns	-	65 m3	32,605	reinforced concrete ringbeams	-	34 m3
Balcony elements	CV	881	fired tiles reinforced concrete	0,02 0,16	10 m ²	6,946	fired tiles reinforced concrete	0,02 0,16	82 m ²	16,796	fired tiles reinforced concrete	0,02 0,16	199 m ²
	NB	160	wooden flooring timber beams	0,02 0,2	10 m ²	1,264	wooden flooring timber beams	0,02 0,2	82 m ²	8,045	wooden flooring CLT	0,02 0,2	193 m ²

Table S2. Division of floorspace in m² across building typologies and urban morphology scenarios for LED and SSP2 development pathways

Floorspace in 2050 (m ²)	LED				SSP2			
	Low rise	Mid rise	High rise	Total	Low rise	Mid rise	High rise	Total
Low Density	4,023,357	1,625,368	74,401	5,723,126	6,115,502	2,470,559	113,089	8,699,150
Medium Density	2,575,406	2,861,563	286,156	5,723,125	3,914,618	4,349,575	434,958	8,699,151
High Density	2,003,094	2,575,406	1,144,625	5,723,125	3,044,703	3,914,618	1,739,830	8,699,151

Table S3. Annual allowable cut, area and forested area per Forest Management Unit in Bhutan.

Source: Annual Forestry Statistics, FMID, 2025

Dzongkhag	Forest Management Unit (FMU)	Year of establishment	Total FMU area (ha)	Forested area (ha)	Annual Allowable Cut (m ³)		
					Commercial	Rural	Total
Bumthang	Dawathang	2000	16,827.80	13,173.47	6,900.00	4,000.00	10,900.00
	Karshong	1994	6,000.36	5,357.58	6,200.00	1,500.00	7,700.00
	Rodungla	2013	14,488.91	12,261.57	12,000.00	2,999.00	14,999.00
Chhukha	Metapchhu	2018	10,676.52	9,789.34	4,000.00	1,030.00	5,030.00
Haa	Haa East	1987	6,221.23	5,003.89	0	500	500
	Lon Chhu	2010	12,568.25	7,789.58	5,300.00	1,000.00	6,300.00
	Sele La	1998	9,114.47	8,207.67	6,790.00	2,440.00	9,230.00
Lhuentse	Rongmanchu	2006	6,400.10	5,567.74	2,700.00	500	3,200.00
Mongar	Korila	1993	12,325.02	9,858.25	1,100.00	2,700.00	3,800.00
	Lingmethang	1997	10,490.15	9,957.59	8,900.00	500	9,400.00
Paro	Bitekha	2006	6,863.23	5,457.76	3,600.00	900	4,500.00
	Zonglela	1992	14,117.99	9,730.03	3,993.71	1,124.71	5,118.42
Pema Gatschel	Khengzore	2019	4,083.24	3,975.71	3,700.00	400	4,100.00
Thimphu	Chamgang-Helela	1993	4,395.06	4,113.10	0	1,800.00	1,800.00
	Gidakom	1977	13,101.25	8,316.53	5,000.00	2,400.00	7,400.00
Trashigang	Khaling	1996	7,035.27	5,255.58	900	400	1,300.00
Trashi Yangtse	Dongdechu	2001	4,857.52	4,776.18	4,100.00	256.75	4,356.75
Trongsa	Chendebji	1996	7,841.94	6,549.58	4,700.00	2,000.00	6,700.00
Wangdue	Gogona	2006	8,080.60	6,774.09	5,161.00	1,167.00	6,328.00
	Khotokha	1984	8,907.29	8,130.10	7,500.00	1,900.00	9,400.00
Zhemgang	Wangdigang	1992	8,759.50	7,688.45	0	2,100.00	2,100.00
Total			193,155.70	157,733.79	92,544.71	31,617.46	124,162.17

Table S4. Timber supply scenarios

Supply scenarios	AAC (m ³ year ⁻¹)	Area under commercial forest management (ha)	Sawnwood conversion (60%)	Sawnwood supply in 2050 (m ³)
Total supply	124,162	193,156	74,497	1,862,433
Timber available for commercial use	92,545	193,156	55,527	1,388,171

Increased production area	142,519	222,685	85,511	2,137,778
Increased harvest intensity	193,156	193,156	115,893	2,897,336
Increased harvest intensity + Increased production area	222,685	222,685	133,611	3,340,278

Table S5. Review of scientific literature of hemp yield values

Source	Yield (dry stems or woody biomass only)	Average yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Country / region
Kołodziej, J. et al. (2023)	7.6 - 11.0 t ha ⁻¹ depending on sowing density and time of harvest	9.3	Pełkowo, Wielkopolska, Poland
Tang et al. (2022)	9.0–12.2 Mg ha ⁻¹ in Daqing, 9.8–16.5 Mg ha ⁻¹ in Lu’an, and 5.2–15.1 Mg ha ⁻¹ in Menghai	11.3	Three locations in China, i.e., Daqing in the northeast, Lu’an in the central-east, and Menghai in the southwest.
Flajšman et al. (2023)	The yield of dry stems was the highest at the Slightly Polluted site and reached 7.3 t ha ⁻¹	7.3	Celje valley, Slovenia
Das et al. (2017)	5.4 t ha ⁻¹ under experimental conditions towards the production of biofuel	5.4	University of Kentucky
Kumar et al. (2025)	5-7.5 t ha ⁻¹ (2-3 tons per acre)	6.3	Uttarakhand, India
Dudziec et al. (2024)	7.6–15 t ha ⁻¹ of dry matter	11.3	Global review
Stramkale et al. (2024)	The ‘Futura 75’ variety achieved the highest stem yield of 31.2 t ha ⁻¹ , and the ‘Futura 83’ variety yielded 28.4 t ha ⁻¹ . The other three fiber hemp varieties produced yields ranging from 19 to 22 t ha ⁻¹	26.7	Latgale in Vilani, Eastern Latvia
Struik et al. (2000)	7.5–12 t ha ⁻¹ ; 9–10 t ha ⁻¹ ; and 5–6 t ha ⁻¹	8.3	Italy, Netherlands and UK respectively on favoured sites and with the best agronomic conditions
Reinhardt et al. (2022)	On favored sites, fiber hemp achieves a stalk yield of 10 t ha ⁻¹ ; However yields on marginal land in the study were at maximum 9.9 t ha ⁻¹ , and on average 7.8 t ha ⁻¹	9.2	Global review of field trial studies on marginal land and in low temperature regions
United Nations (2022)	5.4 - 8.5 t ha ⁻¹	7	France, Italy, the Netherlands and Poland

Table S6. Total timber material demand for Thimphu under each of the adoption rate, urban morphology and development pathway scenarios

Development pathway	Adoption rate	Low density (m3)	Medium density (m3)	High density (m3)
LED	10%	320,233	328,479	341,882
	50%	1,601,161	1,642,394	1,709,407
	90%	2,882,090	2,956,308	3,076,932
SSP2	10%	486,753	499,288	519,660
	50%	2,433,765	2,496,438	2,598,298
	90%	4,380,776	4,493,588	4,676,936

Table S7. Total Hemp material demand for Thimphu under each of the adoption rate, urban morphology and development pathway scenarios

Development pathway	Adoption rate	Low density (m3)	Medium density (m3)	High density (m3)
LED	10%	19,469	29,138	27,271
	50%	97,341	145,686	136,352
	90%	175,214	262,235	245,432
SSP2	10%	29,592	44,289	41,451
	50%	147,958	221,443	207,254
	90%	266,325	398,597	373,057

Table S8. Projected global warming potential of future construction (2025–2050) under varying urban morphology scenarios and material adoption rates, including 100% conventional and 100% nature-based material use

LED	GWP in CO ₂ e (Mt)	SSP2	GWP in CO ₂ e (Mt)
100% adoption, CV construction			
Low density	4.29	Low density	6.52
Medium density	4.18	Medium density	6.36
High density	4.21	High density	6.39
100% adoption, NB construction			
Low density	1.79	Low density	2.72
Medium density	1.73	Medium density	2.63
High density	1.76	High density	2.68
10% adoption of NB construction			
Low density	3.45	Low density	5.25
Medium density	3.37	Medium density	5.12
High density	3.39	High density	5.15
50% adoption of NB construction			
Low density	2.6	Low density	3.95
Medium density	2.53	Medium density	3.84
High density	2.55	High density	3.88
90% adoption of NB construction			
Low density	1.74	Low density	2.65
Medium density	1.69	Medium density	2.57
High density	1.71	High density	2.61

References

- Forest Monitoring and Information Division (FMID). (2025). Annual forestry statistics 2024. Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, Royal Government of Bhutan. Available at: <https://www.dofps.gov.bt/>
- Kołodziej, J., Pudełko, K., & Mańkowski, J. (2023). Energy and biomass yield of industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) as influenced by seeding rate and harvest time in polish agro-climatic conditions. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 20(1), 2159609. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062347>
- Kumar, V., Kumar, R., Ansari, R., & Pandey, M. K. (2025, May). Industrial hemp cultivation in Uttarakhand: India's green gold rush. *Just Agriculture*. Centre for Aromatic Plants. <https://justagriculture.in/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/005-Industrial-Hemp-Cultivation.pdf>
- Dudziec, P., Warmiński, K., & Stolarski, M. J. (2024). Industrial hemp as a multi-purpose crop: Last achievements and research in 2018– 2023. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 21(1), 2369186. DOI:10.1080/15440478.2024.2369186

- Flajšman, M., Košmelj, K., Grčman, H., Ačko, D. K., & Zupan, M. (2023). Industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.)—a valuable alternative crop for growing in agricultural soils contaminated with heavy metals. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(54), 115414-115429.
- Stramkale, V., Andze, L., Cernova, L., Teirumnieka, E., Filipova, I., Stramkalis, A., ... & Andzs, M. (2024). Industrial Hemp Variety Performance in Latvia Under Baltic Sea Climate. *Agronomy*, 14(12), 2750. DOI:10.3390/agronomy14122750
- Reinhardt, J., Hilgert, P., & Von Cossel, M. (2022). Yield performance of dedicated industrial crops on low-temperature characterized marginal agricultural land in Europe—a review. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 16(2), 609-622. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.2314>
- Struik, P. C., Amaducci, S., Bullard, M. J., Stutterheim, N. C., Venturi, G., & Cromack, H. T. H. (2000). Agronomy of fibre hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) in Europe. *Industrial crops and products*, 11(2-3), 107-118
- Tang, K., Wang, J., Yang, Y., Deng, G., Yu, J., Hu, W., ... & Liu, F. (2022). Fiber hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) yield and its response to fertilization and planting density in China. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 177, 114542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.114542>
- United Nations (2022). *Commodities at a glance: Special issue on industrial hemp*. eISBN: 978-92-1-001995-8 https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ditcom2022d1_en.p